

Supplemental figures

Supplemental figure 1) The mean of pronotum length difference between burnt and unburnt areas.

Supplemental figure 2) The mean of pronotum width difference between burnt and unburnt areas.

Supplemental figure 3) The mean of body length difference between burnt and unburnt areas.

Supplemental figure 4) The mean of wing width difference between burnt and unburnt areas.

Supplemental Figure 5) Results of the STRUCTURE analysis from $k = 2$ to $k = 5$ (1= Machico and Santana, 2= Paul da Serra, 3= Ribeira da Vaca and Amparo, 4= Seixal and Fanal, 5= Serra de Agua and Vagum).